

Review of the Impact of Stakeholders' Participation in Rural School Education

Bongani Thulani Gamede, Chinaza Uleanya

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 03, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords</p> <p>Community, Involvement, Management, Participation, Rural Education Stakeholders</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4734190</p>	<p><i>Rural school's education in South Africa is seen as being inefficient for the people it is serving, it is characterized by learner's poor academic performance, lack of qualified teachers which leads to poor teaching and learning, lack of resources as well as poor infrastructure. Meanwhile, the involvement of stakeholders in rural education is expected to proffer solution to the identified challenges. Hence, the reason for this study which explored the impact of stakeholders' participation in rural education in South Africa using review method by reviewing relevant literatures. The finding of the study showed that the reasons for poor academic performances of learners in rural areas of South Africa could be attributed to various factors, however, the role and active participation of rural education stakeholders in salvaging the situation is inevitable. The study therefore recommends that schools should absorb the participative management system where all rural education stakeholders are made to participate in decision-making, and other needful areas. The roles of specific stakeholders should be clearly stated. Also, each of the stakeholder should be duly monitored to ensure their active performance. Meanwhile, periodic workshops should be organised for different rural education stakeholder in order to educate them on their roles and motivate them on the need to perform up to expectation.</i></p>

Introduction

The success or failures of learners in most cases are usually attributed to the learners themselves and the school management (Roman, 2014; Uleanya, Khumalo, Momah & Ndlovu, 2019). A further review of the work of Uleanya, et al (2019) suggests that the adopted leadership style of the school principal is a major factor which determines the success or failures of learners. Conversely, according to Lam (2019), learners' failure is not expected to be overemphasised, rather they are to be made to learn from such experiences. Hence, Lam (2019) holds the view that educators are to give learners room for certain experiences having taught them in the best possible ways. This means that the academic success or failure of learners can somewhat be attributed to their educators. According to Najimi, et al. (2013), issues bothering about curriculum, educator, learning environment, socio-economic background of learners, amongst others are attributed to the reason for learners' academic success or failures. Meanwhile, in many rural settlements in developing and underdeveloped nations which are predominantly African countries, the success or failures of learners are usually attributed to the level of quality education provided (Uleanya, Gamede & Kutame, 2020). This implies that the issue of the quality of education provided to learners in rural settlements seems to be questionable and tends to affect their learning abilities as well as academic performances. On the other hand, poor quality teaching and learning which leads to poverty is considered to be rife in many African countries and this has serious implications for the provision of quality education, especially as it concerns rural schools. According to du Plessis and Mestry (2019), rural schools face severe challenges that are unique to their environment which in turn affects their learning abilities and consequently, academic performances. For instance, lack of parental interest in children's education, insufficient funding from the state, lack of resources, recruitment of underqualified teachers, and multi-grade teaching are some of the identified barriers to effective education (du Plessis & Mestry, 2019). Further review of the work of du Plessis and Mestry (2019) suggests that consciously maximizing stakeholder participation in schools is envisaged to help reduce the various challenges experienced by learners and schools, thereby ensuring the attainment of the desired results. Suffice to state that learning and improvement of learners' academic performances goes beyond the sole efforts of educators, principals, parents, amongst others. Hence, the reason for this study which attempts to explore the impacts that stakeholders' involvement in rural schools can have on the learning abilities and academic performances of learners in such environments. Meanwhile, it is envisaged that there should be a good working relationship amongst all stakeholders in the education system. This is because the main aim for stakeholder participation in rural education is to improve rural education by ensuring

that all needed resources and materials are provided to relevant personnel (Uleanya, Gamede & Kutame, 2020). The value of planning as a path to improved educational outcomes remains undisputed yet there is no definitive evidence that school leaders across South Africa are generally committed to the task of rigorous school improvement planning for improving rural education so that children could benefit. Baldacchino and Farrugia (2002) and Forde (2006) cited in Thompson (2018) have both moaned on the state of educational planning in certain small states and suggested that unsatisfactory performance of the education sector is because of the absence of a culture of planning. Meanwhile, various school leaders tend not to have had formal training in planning and decision making. This suggests that planning as well as decision making amongst rural education stakeholders seems to impact learners in different ways. On the contrary, there are evolving signs which suggests that schools and governments are becoming more aware of the vital need for stakeholders' participation in improving the quality of rural education. However, there seems to be no scientific evidence which suggests the extent to which recognition of planning is transformed to efforts of support. Hence, in some instances, provision of education in rural settlement by the government seems to be irrelevant, whereas, the reverse is to be the case (Uleanya, Gamede & Kutame, 2020). Moreover, stakeholders' participation in school management seems minimal or insignificant. This tends to amount to poor education which affect learners' learning capabilities. Nonetheless, poor education given to learners affect the economy of the nation as the working population continues to produce poor quality material which constitutes decline in the country's productive capacity. Suffice to state that rural education stakeholders' participation: morally, financially and otherwise remains pivot in the quality of education provided to learners as well as their learning abilities and academic performances. Thus the reason for this study which aims at reviewing the impacts of stakeholders' participation in rural schools in South Africa. In order to achieve the aim of the study, attempt would be made at proffering answers to the following identified research questions: What are the impacts of stakeholder participation in education? Which are the factors hindering rural education stakeholders' participation in schools?

Conceptualisation of Terms

The terminologies explained in this section are based on the South African context which is the focus of this study.

Rurality

According to Hlalele (2014), the South African government considers rurality as a term used to imply a kind of way of life, or a state of the mind and a kind of culture which revolves around land, livestock cropping as well as community. This implies that rurality is used majorly characterised by farming either animal or crop, and community settlement. In this study, rurality implies community settlement of low income earners.

Rural Communities

These are areas which are largely characterised by underdevelopment, high rate of poverty, illiteracy, untarred roads, poor electricity supply, poor internet connectivity amongst others (Uleanya & Yu, 2019 and Weeks, 2021). In the context of this study, rural communities imply areas within South Africa that are characterised with high level of illiteracy, unemployment, poverty, untarred and poor road networks.

Rural Schools

Rural schools in the South African context are institutions of learning established in specific strategic locations within and around rural settlements in order to aid development and reduce the rate of illiteracy in such communities (Uleanya & Yu, 2019). In the context of this study, rural schools are used to imply institutions of learning situated in underdeveloped or developing areas of South Africa which are largely characterised by high rate of unemployment, poverty, amongst others.

Rural Education

Review of the work of Hlalele (2014) shows that rural education in South Africa represents the type of unique education made available to people in previously disadvantaged areas. Hlalele (2014) further posits that rural education is in widespread in varying degrees. Rural education is usually aimed at enhancing the programmes and policies of the government which are targeted towards addressing issues of equity, equality and access to education. Rural education tends to be somewhat an afterthought of available education in urban areas (Uleanya, Gamede & Kutame, 2020). In this study, rural education is used to mean the form of education made available to people of historically disadvantaged communities. Thus, by extension rural educator would mean a person who teaches in rural schools in South Africa.

Rural Education Stakeholders

A review of the work of Uleanya, Gamede and Kutame (2020), rural education stakeholders are people or organisations who have influence in the daily operation of happenings in rural institutions of learning. Following the submission of Peláez and Usma (2017), rural education stakeholders can be viewed as rural educational actors. Meanwhile, according to Rahman and Chowdhury (2019), rural education stakeholders include parents, community leaders, all education officers, as well as all teachers such as head and assistant teachers. In this study, rural education stakeholders imply anyone and organisation which has or can have influence over the running of school affairs in rural settlements.

Research Question 1: What are the impacts of stakeholder participation in education?

Review of the work of Peláez and Usma (2017) shows that rural education stakeholders can be categorised into two following their expected responsibilities. These categories are: the administrative rural education stakeholders, and the commercial rural education stakeholders. Each of the categories are explained below following the South African context, thereafter, a third category is identified and explained.

1. Administrative Rural Education Stakeholders

Stakeholders in these categories are identified as those who are mainly responsible for administrative tasks (Peláez & Usma, 2017). According to Peláez and Usma (2017), people in this category are keenly involved in the process of policy making. They engage majorly in activities that ensure the daily smooth running of the rural institution of learning. According to Peláez and Usma (2017), the government such as mayors of municipalities, the principals of schools, heads of department, teachers comprise members of the administrative rural education stakeholders. They are expected to be involved in policy making. Suffice to state that stakeholders in this category are involved in administrative affairs as they pertain to teaching and learning activities, the learning abilities of learners as well as their academic performances.

2. Commercial Rural Education Stakeholders

This category of stakeholders according to Peláez and Usma (2017) is considered to be more involved in supporting school activities through their financial supports. Amongst the commercial rural education stakeholders are local and international banks, as well as other industries which includes tourism and hospitality such as hotels, games and resort, amongst others. Suffice to state that stakeholders in this categories are largely involved in financially supporting schools in order to achieve the desired results.

3. Other Rural Education Stakeholders

Sequel to the submission of Uleanya, Gamede and Kutame (2020), those within this category would revolve around parents of learners, community members, peers, amongst others. Those in this category have influence on the learning abilities of learners in various capacities. Stakeholders in this category are involved in supporting learners in various forms. Their impact on learners cannot be specifically stated. Their impacts cut across finance

Additionally, according to Peláez and Usma (2017), for successful impacts to be made by rural education stakeholders, active role and a sense of mutual responsibilities amongst the various categories of and stakeholders is desired. Hence, in the context of this study, as it concerns the nation South Africa, there is need to consider the role of the Department of Basic Education (DBE) in ensuring that there is full participation in rural education.

Management plan supporting staff participation in decision making

The officials of the Department of Basic education should have the management plan which talks to the participation of all stakeholders in the management and decision making of the school. It is very important for the Department of Basic Education in the twenty-first century to develop a management plan which favours staff participation in decision making. Somech (2002, 341) maintains that participative management is rooted in the management style which focuses on the sharing of power in order to achieve organisational goals. Power-sharing is viewed as way of enhancing staff morale and such has made productivity to become a cornerstone of the post-apartheid management of public institutions such as South African schools.

Involvement of relevant stakeholders in decision-making processes

The Department of Basic education should involve all stakeholders if necessary in decision making, this is because of the fact that stakeholders' involvement in decision making is critical for effective school management and learners' academic improvement. The South African Schools Act (Act No.84 of 1996) (South Africa 1996b) makes provision for stakeholders such as parents and trade unions to be involved in a school's decision-making processes. The management styles of school principals should embrace the concept of

stakeholder involvement in decision-making processes. According to Marishane et al. (2013), since democratisation in South Africa, successful government efforts have been made to involve stakeholders in decisions that affect them.

School governing bodies (SGBs) participating in school matters

It is so significant that principals should allow SGB members to participate on school matters and take informed decisions. The parents' voice is represented in schools through participation in SGBs. Parents are expected to take control of the formal education of their children by means provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa Act (Act 108 of 1996) (South Africa 1996a). Furthermore, Marishane et al. (2013) hold the view that the South African government enjoins parents to be involved in the formal education of their children. Community members as well as children are envisaged to benefit from the participation of parents in school affairs.

Learners participate in decision-making processes through Representative Councils of Learners (RCLs)

The Department of Basic education should encourage learners to participate in decision-making processes through representative councils of learners (RCLs). Learner participation in decision-making processes assist them in preparing them for leadership roles in the community. According to Marishane et al. (2013), in the 21st century, learners are to be managed with a view of developing them towards becoming future leaders, first, within the school environment and later their communities. The responsibility therefore lies with the school management team to unlock the potential of learners in order for them to be able lead in future (Marishane et al., 2013). This implies that following the new developments and changes within the South African education system, school management teams are expected to change their attitude towards the role and importance of learners in school management.

Principals to be trained on how to facilitate participative management

Principals and their school management teams should be trained as to how to facilitate participative management in their schools. There is a great need for the KwaZulu-Natal Department of Basic Education to invest in human capital by training and developing the school management teams. Marishane et al. (2013) hold the view that participatory models are centred on the idea that the organisation has staff members who are professionally highly trained, have a certain expertise, and therefore should participate in decision making. The financial resources components may have to be allocated for training of principals, and other school management team members on how to facilitate participative management.

Staff members to be given adequate time to discuss school matters

The Department should encourage principals to give stakeholders adequate time to discuss school matters relating to rural education. Marland (2011) states that decision making in schools are expected to be duly informed, and considered carefully on the basis of time factors as well as participatory practises. In other words, for schools to be productive in their work environment and to ensure good quality, there is need for planning and proper time allocation for staff as part of the education stakeholders in rural education.

The use trade union representatives for staff participation

The Department of Basic Education is expected to promote and encourage the use trade union representatives for staff participation. In the post-apartheid South Africa, educators have regarded trade unions as their mouthpiece when talking to employers such as the Department of Basic Education. The Departmental employees have increasingly demanded the chance to exercise their democratic right regarding school matters. However, following the work of Mestry (2017), the use of participatory approach in school affairs does not imply principals turning control of the organisation to the employees. Neither does it mean that employees have veto power over school principals, or that any bureaucratic management style is never used.

Research Question 2: Which are the factors hindering rural education stakeholders' participation in schools?

Rural education has some problems and the devolution of decision-making power to school and community does not automatically result in exercise of devolved power due to a number of factors such as social structure, attitude and culture of individuals and organizations, and political intervention in stakeholder participation. Contextual understanding of participation is of primary importance to clarify diversity in the results of stakeholder participation in rural school education in a developing nation such as South Africa.

Structure of Governance

The structure of governance in rural schools impacts on the involvement of education stakeholders in such societies (Nthontho, 2017). For instance, according to Mncube and Harber (2013), in South Africa, children are involved in the governance structures of schools, however, their inclusion is somewhat insignificant. This implies that the way and manner rural school governance structure is designed influences the involvement of the stakeholders in the rural education system in such environment.

Individual Attitude and Organizational Culture

Different people have varying attitude following their perceptions. The attitude of individual rural education stakeholder influences their involvement in matters of the schools and learners (Mokoena, 2011). According to Mokoena (2011), the involvement and contribution of different rural education stakeholder is largely dependent on their perceptions, values, understanding, attitudes, knowledge, experiences and feelings regarding issues revolving around the schools and learners. Similarly, suffice to state that the involvement of organisations as part of the rural education stakeholders are largely dependent on their values, amongst other factors towards the schools and the learners.

Lack of Infrastructures and Technological Facilities

The lack of Infrastructures and technological facilities in the 21st century affects rural education stakeholders from participating as expected in the happenings of the schools. According to Uleanya, Gamede and Kutame (2020), lack of necessary infrastructures hinder different rural education stakeholders from performing their expected roles. Meanwhile, following a review of the work of Akintolu and Uleanya (2021), digital divide tends to have effect in the participation of different rural education stakeholders. However, Bower (2010) cited in Uleanya and Gamede (2018) suggests the need for improvisation where possible. This implies that rural education stakeholders can be limited and inefficient where the necessary facilities needed for efficient discharge of their duties are not available.

Government Policies

Dealings and activities of rural education stakeholders are expected to be guided by the policies of the government. The work of Uleanya and Yu (2019) shows that policies of the government are crucial and important in determining the existence and survival of institutions such as rural schools. This also extends to the participation of rural education stakeholders in South Africa.

Skills and Experienced Man-power

Shortage of skills and experienced manpower is considered a limiting factor in South Africa (Ntuli & Allopi, 2014). Certain skills are needed by the Department of Basic education (DBE) for ensuring that there is growth in all educational activities inclusive of those pertaining to rural schools. Meanwhile, rural communities are usually encompassed with many unskilled individuals due to migration of labour and skilled manpower to urban centers, the few people who are left in rural areas need to be utilized for the benefit of schools in rural communities. Dani and Shah (2016) express the need for trainings to be given to individuals in rural communities, these trainings are expected to empower individuals and make them useful to both themselves and the society. This is envisaged to be of help in such environments.

Orientation

Uleanya and Rugbeer (2020) hold the view that orientation is paramount in order to successfully engage people in certain activities. This implies that the orientation given to individual rural education stakeholders on their involvement and participation in activities of the schools and those of learners influence their response in such regard. For instance, individual rural education stakeholders who are well oriented on the schooling activities are likely to know the importance of their participation, thus, show more involvement and participate better, compared to those who are not. Meanwhile, both individuals and societies are likely to get involved in activities of the schools if they are well oriented and know that there are some forms of benefits for the community and their children who are the learners in this instance. However, the reverse is likely to be the case when the wrong orientation is given to individuals or when the orientation given is inadequate.

Lack of Motivation

Review of the works of Estay, Durrieu and Akhter (2013) as well as Gamede and Uleanya (2018) suggest that lack of motivation hampers the creation and sustainability of an institution. In the context of this study, rural schools. Estay, Durrieu and Akhter (2013) as well as Gamede and Uleanya (2018) further hold the view that individuals who are motivated to uphold their educational activities are more profitable. In other words, it is important to note that productive people are the product of motivation amidst challenges. Motivation in this regard can be viewed from either intrinsic or extrinsic (Cherry, 2018 and Cherry, 2020). Intrinsic motivation implies that rural education stakeholders are passionate and moved to meet set desired goals and needs,

regardless of the challenges that they may encounter, rather than being enthused by the desire for external rewards such as money, fame and recognition (Cherry, 2018 and Cherry, 2020). Conversely, extrinsic motivation implies rural education stakeholders in South Africa being moved to achieve set goals against all odds following certain external rewards like fame, prize, money, and recognition. Meanwhile, lack of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is likely to demoralize rural education stakeholders, thereby not making them deliver on their set tasks.

School Related Factors

Rural schools have certain related factors which can be contributory to promoting or hindering participation of stakeholders in their activities. For instance, rural schools regardless of their location have major roles to perform in order to ensure that learners are inspired and motivated to become productive in their societies. Thus, the role of stakeholders may likely thrive in rural communities when schools in such communities ensure that learners get involved in educational activities within such environments and are motivated to continuously perform such activities with the aim of proffering solutions to existing challenges and demands in such environments. Vis-à-vis, the reverse is likely to be the case if stakeholders fail to get involved. Suffice to state that institutions of learning in rural based communities are expected to conduct activities which will promote educational activities, thereby ensuring sustainable development in such environments and for the individuals involved. However, such activities would likely thrive better when stakeholders are duly involved and participate.

Conclusion

The study explored the impacts of rural education stakeholders on the learning abilities of learners. Review method was adopted, hence, relevant literatures were reviewed. In order to achieve the aim of the study, attempts were made to proffer answers to the two identified research questions guiding the study. The questions are: What are the impacts of stakeholder participation in education? Which are the factors hindering rural education stakeholders' participation in schools? The findings of the study showed that the reason for learners' poor academic performances in rural areas in South Africa can be attributed to different factors such as poor time management, lack of infrastructures, poor improvisation, poor leadership, lack of educators, amongst others. However, principal of the factors is lack of adequate involvement of rural education stakeholders. Suffice to state that the role of rural education stakeholders such as community members and leaders, industries, government at various levels, parents of learners, learners themselves, amongst others is pivot. Thus, the need for collaborative efforts from all rural education stakeholders in ensuring the achievement of the desired success remains crucial. However, the findings of the study also suggest that several factors militate against and hinder certain rural education stakeholders from actively participating as expected. This in turn affects the learners in different ways and capacities, consequently affects their academic performances.

Recommendations

Sequel to the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- Schools should absorb the participative management system. In this regard, all rural education stakeholders would be made to participate in decision-making and other affairs of the school and academic lives of learners. This can be achieved by encouraging regular meetings where matters concerning the schools and learners' affairs are discussed in details.
- The roles of specific stakeholders should be clearly stated. In this case, all stakeholder would know the different expectations and action point to be carried out. Stakeholders should be made to give reports following tasks assigned to them during their regular meetings.
- Adequate orientation should be given to rural education stakeholders on the need to participate in the activities that concern the running of the schools and the learners. This can be done through periodic workshops which can be organised for different rural education stakeholder in order to educate them on their roles and motivate them on the need to perform up to expectation.
- The necessary facilities and infrastructures needed for rural education stakeholders to discharge their duties appropriately should be made available. This could be done through the office of the government or other stakeholders such as the commercial rural education stakeholders.
- Each of the stakeholder should be duly monitored to ensure their active performance.

Suggestion for Further Study

Meanwhile, the study was limited to only review of relevant literatures which were adapted to the context of rural South African environments and schools. Hence, it is suggested that further studies be conducted in this

regard empirically. Quantitative or mixed methods can be adopted for data collection, whilst rural areas in two or more countries within or outside Africa are compared.

References

- Akintolu, M. and Uleanya, C. (2021). Ensuring Sustainable Development Goal in Rural Africa through Adult Literacy Programme: A Case Study of Technology Usage in Developing Nations. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(12c)
- Baldacchino, G., & Farrugia, C. J. (2002). Educational planning in small states: Concepts and experiences. *Commonwealth Secretariat*.
- Botha, K.F.H. (2013). Self-regulation as Psychological Strength in South Africa: A Review. In *Well-Being Research in South Africa*. DOI: 10.1007/978-94-007-6368-5_23
- Bower, J. (2010). Poor Pedagogy + Technology = Accelerated Malpractice. Online available from: <http://www.joebower.org>. Accessed 29th October 2018.
- Cherry, K. (2020). Differences of Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation. Available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/differences-between-extrinsic-and-intrinsic-motivation-2795384>. Accessed 10 March 2021
- Cherry, K. (2018). 5 Components of emotional intelligence. *Very Well Mind*. Available at: <https://www.verywellmind.com/components-of-emotional-intelligence-2795438>. Accessed 10 March 2021
- Dani, S. & Shah, S. (2016). Call and Definition of Rural University. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, vol. 7 (1), 64–66.
- du Plessis, P., & Mestry, R. (2019). Teachers for rural schools - a challenge for South Africa. *South African Journal of Education*, 39(Suppl. 1), s1-s9. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15700/saje.v39ns1a1774>
- Estay, C. Durrieu, F., & Akhter, M. (2013). Entrepreneurship: From motivation to start-up. *Journal of International Entrepreneurship*, 11 (3), 243–267
- Forde, G. (2006). Educational planning in the Eastern Caribbean: A strategic approach. *Education Media International*, 25(3), 186–191.
- Gamede, B.T. & Uleanya, C. (2018). Entrepreneurship: Solution to Unemployment in Rural Communities. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*. 21(1), 101-122.
- Hlalele, D. (2014). Rural Education in South Africa: Concepts and Practices. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(4), 462-469. DOI: 10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n4p462.
- Lam, R. (2019). What students do when encountering failure in collaborative tasks. *npj Science of Learning*, 4 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41539-019-0045-1>.
- Marishane, R.N. van der Merwe, H. M., Van Zyl, A.E. & Zengele, V.T.Z. (2013) *The effective management of a school*. Pretoria: van Schaik Publishers.
- Marland, M. (2011). *School management skills*. London: Heinemann.
- Mestry, R. (2017). Empowering principals to lead and manage public schools effectively in the 21st century. *South African Journal of Education*, 37(1), 1-11. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15700/saje.v37n1a1334>
- Mncube, V.S. & Harber, C. (2013). Learners' democratic involvement in school governing bodies in South Africa: Making the voice of the voiceless heard, *SA-eDUC Journal* 10(1), 1-24.
- Mokoena, S. (2011). Participative Decision-making: Perceptions of School Stakeholders in South Africa. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 29(2), 119-131
- Najimi, A., Sharifirad, G., Amini, M.M., & Meftagh, S.D. (2013). Academic failure and students' viewpoint: The influence of individual, internal and external organizational factors. *Journal of education and health promotion*, 2, 22. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2277-9531.112698>
- Nthonto, M. (2017). Children as stakeholders in education: Does their voice matter?. *South African Journal of Childhood Education*, 7(1), 1-7. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v7i1.434>
- Ntuli, B., & Allopi, D. (2014). Impact of Inadequate Experience and Skill on the Construction Sector in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 4(1), 570-575
- Peláez, O., & Usma, J. (2017). The Crucial Role of Educational Stakeholders in the Appropriation of Foreign Language Education Policies: A Case Study. *PROFILE*, 19(2), 121-134. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15446/profile.v19n2.57215>.
- Rahman, S., & Chowdhury, S.R. (2019). Exploring The Perception of Different Stakeholders in Rural Area of Bangladesh's Kindergarten Schools. *IJARIE*, 5(6), 843-852. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.22350.00329
- Roman, M.D. (2014). Students' Failure in Academic Environment. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 114, 170–177. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.679.
- Somech, A. (2002). Explicating the Complexity of Participative Management: An Investigation of Multiple Dimensions. *Educational Administration Quarterly* 38(3):341-371. DOI: 10.1177/00161X02038003004.

- South African Schools Act No. 84 of 1996. Government Gazette: Pretoria
- Thompson, C.S. (2018). School Administrators' and Stakeholders' Attitudes Toward, and Perspectives on School Improvement Planning
- Uleanya, C. & Gamede, B.T. (2018). Correlates of Pedagogic Malpractices. *The Independent Journal of Teaching and Learning (The IJTL)*, 13(2), 36-52.
- Uleanya, C., Gamede, B.T., & Kutame, A.P. (2020). Rural and Irrelevant: exploration of learning challenges among undergraduates' rural Universities. *African Identities Journal*, vol. 18, (4), 377-391, DOI: 10.1080/14725843.2020.1767037.
- Uleanya, C., Khumalo, N.P., Momah, E. & Ndlovu, B.B. (2019). Contextualising Leadership Paradigm as a Determinant for Academic Success: A Case Study of Secondary Schools in Nigeria and South Africa. *Journal of Gender, Information & Development in Africa*, 8(1), 188-207 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31920/2050-4284/2019/8n1a10>.
- Uleanya, C., & Yu, K. (2019). Review of Preparedness of Rural African Communities Nexus Formal Education in The Fourth Industrial Revolution. *South African Review of Sociology*. 50(3-4), 91-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21528586.2019.1639074>.
- Weeks, S.G. (2021). Rural Education: International Context. Available at: <https://education.stateuniversity.com/pages/2382/Rural-Education-INTERNATIONAL-CONTEXT.html>. Accessed 18 March 2021.

Author Information

Bongani Thulani Gamede
 University of Zululand
 KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa

Chinaza Uleanya
 University of Johannesburg
 Gauteng, South Africa
